

To Evaluate The Effectiveness Of Structured Teaching Programme On Knowledge Regarding Dyslexia Among Primary School Teachers In Selected Schools Of Navi Mumbai

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Abstract:

Dyslexia is the most common of the language based learning disabilities. As National Center for Education statistics, 5% of all adults are “non-literate”, 20-25% of all adults can only read at the lowest level, 62% of nonreaders dropped out of high school. 80% of children with an IEP have reading difficulty and 85% of those are Dyslexic. The aim of study is to evaluate the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding dyslexia among primary school teachers. **Material and methods:** The research approach adopted for the study evaluative method to assess the objective by using Pre experimental research design. 200 primary school teachers, 100 control and 100 experimental group data are collected from Navi Mumbai by using non-probability purposive sampling technique. Data was collected after Pre-test followed by Structured teaching programme and post -test on 7th day. **Results:** Findings related to effectiveness of structured teaching programme mean scores- pre and post-test compared with control and experimental group shows difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), for control group, the mean pre-test and post-test total knowledge score were 14.16 and 13.79 ,Whereas experimental group it was 14.45 and 21.02 which shows increase in knowledge after STP. Findings related to the association between pre interventional knowledge score and their selected demographic variables did not shown any significant difference. **Conclusion:** This indicates that structured teaching program helps to improve the on knowledge of primary school teachers.

Keywords: *Structured Teaching Programme, Knowledge Regarding Dyslexia, Primary School Teachers, effectiveness of structured teaching programme, Dyslexia*

Introduction

Teacher plays important role in student’s life. A student in early age is like blank sheet that can be colored beautifully with the pool of teachers’ knowledge. After family, teacher paves the foundation for student’s growth or can say they play very crucial role in foundation of society and ultimately nation, especially for country like India which contribute majority of younger population. So it’s clear enough, that students should be developed and encouraged to learn in every part of country and thus teachers become architect here to mold students by bearing responsibility on their own shoulders¹. If teachers are unaware about major issues

associated with learning, there won't be good learning for the students to develop and make them incapable to stand on their own feet in near future.²

Dyslexia affects areas of the brain that process language. To improve child's learning first teacher should possess sound knowledge regarding reading and writing problems.³ People with dyslexia could not able to pronounce the words or sentences correctly due to failing to read correctly. It affects children differently according to their severity and majors done by parents and teachers. Few children with dyslexia can manage to learn as they receive excellent instructions and diagnosed early, but if not diagnosed it affects child's self-image and they feel low and less capable for study which leads to poor academic performance and increases school drop outs.⁴

According to the National assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP), all 4th ranking students are "below basic" reading skills are almost 38%. They are below the 40th percentile for their stage group. Nationwide 20% of the elementary school population is struggling with reading.⁵ In Mumbai, study was conducted on learning disability. Researcher included students with difficulty in reading and writing and found that around 72.76 percent of students got less grades due to learning problems.⁶

In small towns, there are lack of specialty clinics as well as trained personnel who are expert in identification of learning difficulties specially dyslexia. Study conducted in schools of Bikaner city involving students from grade 3rd to 5th. Students undergone the set of questions called as screening tool for dyslexia and found 48 students suffer from dyslexia.⁷

Need for the Study

Exploratory study was conducted to evaluate the awareness and attitude of primary school teachers towards learning problems in calculations at initial schooling. It feels that learning disability is nothing but cluster of symptoms which indicates difficulties faced by child during conventional classroom instruction. Acquiring language skills such as reading, spelling, writing comprehension becomes difficult for children during this phase. Students find it difficult in coping up with flow of academic curriculum and secure poor marks due to difficulties in understanding basic concepts. As per study, such level of difficulty, which is not identified, can result into prolonged consequences like drop out & behavioral disorders.⁸

According to Dyslexia Association of India, Children with academic difficulties and with clumsy behavior, particularly accident prone, are more likely to suffer Dyslexia compared to normal child. International Dyslexia Association suggests few dyslexic patterns in child such as frustration, depression, anxiety and self-doubt, low self-esteem is because of unawareness about own learning disabilities. Such children are sensitive and fragile which can only be managed by early diagnosis and effective knowledge on learning difficulties by teachers.

It follows from the above that all teachers need basic knowledge of the learning difficulties. The same conclusion can be drawn from a number of studies in which it was found that knowledge of teachers play crucial role in determining learning difficulties in early age.¹⁰

As per above literature and researcher observation in school students and teachers, it is found that a research study can be done on teachers to enhance their knowledge about dyslexia and to make student's learning productive to stand them on their own feet. Researcher also has her own experience in teaching NGO, where researcher found dyslexic child remained undiagnosed and that lead to poor performance and academic failure made child quiet and depressed. This researcher's curiosity compelled him to pursue this subject as a research study in order to raise awareness, increase instructor understanding, and eventually make the students' lives better and brighter.

Aim of the Study

The main aim of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding dyslexia among primary school teachers in selected schools of Navi Mumbai.

Methodology

The evaluative research approach was adopted to determine the effectiveness of a structured teaching program on knowledge regarding dyslexia among primary school teachers. The quasi-experimental research design that is a non-randomized control group design used to test the hypothesis and achieve the desired objective. This study was proposed to be conducted among primary school teachers in selected schools of Navi Mumbai. 200 samples are those who teach in primary schools -1st to 4th standard in schools of Navi Mumbai. They were selected by a Non-probability purposive sampling method. Even after prior appointments, if subjects were found busy in their emergency work, care was taken not to interrupt them in their work and again suitable time was taken.

The study tool was filled personally by interviewing the subjects. The sample characteristics were described using frequency and percentage. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to assess the effectiveness of structured teaching. The content validity and reliability of the tool were done, which suggested that the tool was reliable. The pilot study was done on 10 control groups and 10 experimental group samples and found that the study was feasible for the final study. The data obtained was analyzed in terms of the objective of the study using descriptive and inferential statistics. The plan of data analysis was developed under the excellent direction of experts in the field nursing and statistics.

Results

Analysis of data related to demographic variables under study represents gender wise distribution as majority female 58% and 55% of the control and experimental group respectively. In age wise distribution of primary teachers as Out of 100 control group participants, majority of teachers 36-45 years were 44% whereas in 100 experimental participants, 40% were belongs 25-35 years of age.

In control group majority of 42% participants had 10-20 years of experience whereas in experimental group 37% participants have less than 10 years of experience. 77% control group participants and 89% of experimental group participants completed their D.Ed. whereas

23% and 11% of control and experimental group participants completed their M.Ed. Participants in the control group worked in the private sector 100% and 80% of the participants in the experimental group worked in the public sector and 20% in private sector.

100% of Control group teachers had 30 class strength, whereas 80% of the experimental participants had 30 students to handle and 20% of them had 60 children in their class. 75% and 25% of control group participants teach in English and Marathi medium respectively whereas in experimental group 80% and 20% of participants teach in English and Marathi medium. Awareness regarding dyslexia data shows no one of the participants had attended any special training on dyslexia.

Figure 1 Experience wise distribution of primary school teachers

Findings related to the knowledge before structured teaching programme regarding dyslexia among primary school teachers shows that there is no difference in the pretest scores between the participants in the control group and experimental group using as Mann-Whitney u test as the value is greater than 0.05.

Findings related to the knowledge after structured teaching programme regarding dyslexia among primary school teachers. Level of knowledge after structured teaching programme regarding dyslexia among primary school teachers shows that by using a Mann-Whitney test to compare the means of two independent groups we found that there was a statistically significant difference in the mean knowledge scores between experimental and control groups. The p value is less than 0.05 so there is increase in knowledge after structured teaching programme.

Domain wise analysis of knowledge after STP regarding dyslexia among primary school teachers show meaning of dyslexia domain, experimental group had a mean score of 2.59 whereas control group had a mean score of 2.31. This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). For the domain type of dyslexia, experimental group had a mean score of 2.9 whereas control group had a mean score of 2.34. This difference was statistically significant

($p < 0.001$). For risk factor domain of dyslexia, experimental group had a mean score of 0.76 whereas control group had a mean score of 0.43. This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). For misconceptions of dyslexia domain, experimental group had a mean score of 0.84 whereas control group had a mean score of 0.59. This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). For signs and symptoms of dyslexia domain, experimental group had a mean score of 8.05 whereas control group had a mean score of 4.03. This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). For management of dyslexia domain, experimental group had a mean score of 5.87 whereas control group had a mean score of 4.03. This difference was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). The means of total knowledge score was 36.15 in experimental group and 24.81 in control group. Hence there was statistically significant difference in the mean scores ($p < 0.001$).

Table 1 Domain wise analysis of knowledge after STP regarding dyslexia among primary school teachers

POST TEST		MEAN	SD	Z VALUE	P VALUE
Meaning	Control	2.31	0.65	-3.088	.002
	Experimental	2.59	0.51		
Type	Control	2.34	0.88	-4.343	.000
	Experimental	2.9	0.88		
Risk factor	Control	0.43	0.5	-4.742	.000
	Experimental	0.76	0.43		
Mis-conception	Control	0.59	0.49	-3.906	.000
	Experimental	0.84	0.37		
Signs & Symptoms	Control	4.75	1.74	-10.799	.000
	Experimental	8.05	1.07		
Management	Control	4.03	1.84	-7.229	.000
	Experimental	5.87	1.32		
Total score	Control	13.79	2.09	-11.992	.000
	Experimental	21.01	1.68		

Findings related to effectiveness of structured teaching programme on knowledge regarding dyslexia among primary school teachers are as follows: Effectiveness of STP on knowledge

regarding dyslexia among primary school teachers shows that control group, the pre-test and post-test scores were compared with each other using Wilcoxon sign rank test and the p value is not less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) which means that there is no difference in knowledge statistically.

Effectiveness of STP on knowledge regarding dyslexia among primary school teachers findings of the experimental group, there was significant increase in the post test scores of mean. Compared the pre-test and post- test score and calculated p value by Wilcoxon rank test. P value ($p < 0.05$) less than 0.05 hence we can conclude that there is increase in knowledge after structured teaching programme.

Table 2 Effectiveness of STP on knowledge regarding dyslexia among primary school teacher’s findings of the control and experimental group

knowledge regarding dyslexia among primary school teachers	Control Group		Experimental Group	
	Pretest	Post test	Pretest	Post test
Mean	14.16	13.79	14.45	21.01
SD	2.07	2.09	2.02	1.68
Z-value	-1.55		-8.53	
P-value	0.121		0	

Figure 2 Effectiveness of STP on knowledge regarding dyslexia among primary school teacher’s findings of the control and experimental group

Findings related to find out the association between pre interventional knowledge score and their selected demographic variables shows that, there is no significant association between the pre interventional knowledge score and their selected demographic variables

Discussion

Study findings indicated that gender wise distribution of primary teachers as majority 58% and 55% were females respectively, Age group 36-45 years were 44% , Experience wise distribution of primary teachers 42% had teaching experience of 10-20 years, Education qualification majority of the teachers completed D.Ed. in control 77% and experimental group 89%, Working sector 80% of the participants in the experimental group worked in the public sector, Strength of class wise distribution of primary teachers were 30 children whereas 80% of the experimental participants, Language medium wise distribution of primary teachers as among the controls, 75% of the participants taught in English medium schools whereas 80% of the experimental participants taught in English medium, Special training attended on Dyslexia wise distribution of primary teachers as No one of the participants had attended any special training on dyslexia.

A similar study conducted by Anil Shetty, et al. (2014) conducted study to evaluate the awareness and knowledge of school teachers in India. The self-report questionnaire was circulated to the teachers of 314 teachers from 32 schools, after that researcher categorized responses into 4 groups according answered appropriately sign and symptoms of dyslexia. Result shown that there was direct relation with the training attended by teachers prior to their knowledge .Only 18 teachers identified sign and symptom more than 11. Study concluded that 66.2% teachers were having poor knowledge about dyslexia.¹¹

Researcher compared data of both the groups of control and experimental group. Researcher conducted pre-test followed by structured teaching programme and after that on 7th day conducted post-test Investigator analyzed data by descriptive and inferential statistics. Results shows that, there is effectiveness of structured teaching programme and experimental group was shown pre-test score was 13.79 (58%) to 21.01 (84%).

A Study conducted by Joy priscilla (2013) on a study to evaluate the effect of structured teaching programme on dyslexia and its identification among school teachers in selected primary schools of Bengaluru , three settings of the school were selected by researcher and participants those who teach to 6-12 years of children ,non-probability purposive sampling used by the investigator data analyzed by use of descriptive and inferential statistics, total 40 subjects involved in study , the researcher conducted the pre-test score of subjects and post-test knowledge assessed after structured teaching programme and knowledge increased from 19.38 (41.22%) to 39.53 (84.10%). Result concluded that there is effectiveness is assessed by the researcher and need to update teachers knowledge.¹²

Conclusion

According to Dyslexia Association of India, Children with academic snags and with clumsy actions, particularly accident susceptible, are more likely to suffer Dyslexia compared to normal child. Students find it tough in managing with flow of academic curriculum and secure poor marks due to difficulties in understanding basic concepts. As per studies its difficult phase for the kids from kindergarten to primary school and such

level of difficulty, which is not identified can result into prolonged consequences like drop out & behavioral disorders.

Findings of knowledge before structured teaching programme regarding dyslexia among primary school teachers shows that, there is no difference (more than 0.05) in the pre-test scores between the participants in the control group and experimental group using as Mann-Whitney test done as data comes under non-parametric curve. The value of Mann-Whitney test is calculated from table value p.

By use of Mann-Whitney test assessed the knowledge after structured teaching programme value p value calculated from table values. There was significant difference in the post test knowledge score of experimental group, which was compared with control group's post-test knowledge mean score.

Researcher used Wilcoxon-rank test used for assessing effectiveness of STP on knowledge regarding dyslexia in primary school teachers, domain wise analysis done by the researcher and the total knowledge mean score of pre-test (24.79) with post-test (24.8) of control and experimental group of pre-test (14.45) with post-test (21.01) was compared, and mean score of knowledge depicts that, there is significant ($p < 0.05$) difference seen by use of structured teaching to enhance the knowledge of primary school teachers.

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